

The Influence of Promotions and Interest Rates on ASN Customer Decisions in Taking Consumer Credit PT Bank Sulselbar Cabang Parepare

Andi Alfianto Anugrah Ilahi^{1*}, Arifuddin², Firman Alimuddin³
Andi Sapada Institute, South Sulawesi

Corresponding Author: Andi Alfianto Anugrah Ilahi alvian260@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to find out whether promotions and interest rates have a partial and simultaneous effect on ASN customers' decisions in taking consumer credit at PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch. Multiple linear regression is the analytical technique employed, along with partial and simultaneous tests for validity, reliability, and hypothesis testing. The study's findings indicate that promotion (X1) has a somewhat substantial impact on ASN customers' decisions in taking consumer credit at PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch, this is shown based on the calculated promotional t value of $4.431 > t$ table 1.967 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, the interest rate (X2) has a positive and partially significant effect on ASN customers' decisions in taking consumer credit at PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch, this is shown by the calculated t value of $13.627 > t$ table 1.967 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. All Pearson correlation or calculated r values from statements related to promotions and interest rates have an r table value greater than 0.107 , so all instruments are declared valid. Simultaneously promotions and interest rates influence ASN customers' decisions in taking consumer credit at PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch, this is shown based on the calculated F value of $5,035.590 > F$ table 3.023 , with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$.

INTRODUCTION

Banks play a vital part in propelling the economic expansion of a nation. The growth of a nation's banks can be considered an indicator of that country's progress. As a country achieves progress, the role played by banking institutions becomes increasingly important in controlling that country, indicating that the existence of the banking sector is increasingly needed by the government and society.

PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch understands the needs of ASN and is committed to providing services that meet their expectations. Through the consumer credit promotions offered, ASN have the opportunity to get loans with more favourable terms and an easier process. These promotions may include offering competitive interest rates, flexible repayment periods, or even waiving administration fees. By taking advantage of consumer credit promotions and good interest rates provided by Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch, ASN can plan their finances better.

The researcher concluded that research on the influence of promotions and interest rates on new customers of PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch will be a relevant and important topic for further investigation. This research aims to understand the impact of promotions offered by banks and the interest rates given on potential new customers' decisions to join the bank. In the context of PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch, this research will provide a deeper understanding of the extent to which consumer credit promotions and good interest rates influence the interest of potential new customers to become customers at the bank. The researcher took several references from previous research related to promotions and interest rates such as research conducted by which explains that promotions have a positive and significant influence on decisions. Meanwhile, in research conducted by (Putra, 2021), it is proven that there is a significant influence between interest rates and customer decisions in deciding to take consumer credit in banking, in this case banks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing Management

The company plans and executes marketing management activities. Planning calls for the appropriate approach and knowledge to establish the plan. A company's marketing management plays a critical part in developing more inventive products, determining the company's target market share, and introducing new products to prospective customers (Tijjang & Rahmawati, 2021), The method is total marketing management. a company does business by preparing, determining and distributing ideas, goods, and services that are able to satisfy the target market's demands (Ilahi et al., 2023), also explains that the goal of marketing management is to create and provide high-quality sales in order to draw in, hold on to, and grow the consumer base.

The marketing management process involves a series of steps taken by a company to plan, implement and control marketing activities with the aim of meeting customer needs and desires and achieving business goals. The

following is the management process according to (Arifuddin & Alimudin, 2023)

1. Analyse commercial prospects

Businesses who are attempting to advertise their goods deal with a variety of circumstances. In this situation, companies need to take advantage of the chances that present themselves. In order for the organization to comprehend the current market prospects, a review of its market opportunities is required.

2. Examine and decide which market to target.

Following the study of market opportunities, the firm is prepared to choose a target market and begin research. Businesses need to be able to estimate and compute market attractiveness while accounting for the overall size, growth, and profitability of the market.

3. Creating a plan for the market

After the target market has been chosen and researched, it is time to decide on the market strategy that will be applied in marketing initiatives. The business must decide how it will vary.

Types of Flowers

(Budiman & Susanty, 2014) suggests that there are two. The types of interest given to customers include:

1. Savings Interest

This is the purchase price that the bank must pay to the customer who owns the deposit. This interest is given as stimulation or compensation to customers who save their money in the bank. For example, current account services, savings interest and deposit interest.

2. Loan interest

Is the interest charged to borrowers (debtors) or the selling price that must be paid by the borrowing customer to the bank, loan interest is the selling price/credit interest.

METHODOLOGY

In quantitative research, (Darmawan & Latifah, 2013) data analysis activities are divided into two, namely the activities of describing data and carrying out statistical tests. The activity of describing data is describing existing data in order to obtain a real form from respondents, so that it is easier for researchers or other people who are interested in the results of the research to be understood to understand. Activities to describe data can be carried out using descriptive statistical measurements. The Likert scale is used to measure the attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. With a Likert scale, the variables to be measured are translated into indicator variables. Then these indicators are used as a starting point for compiling instrument items which can be in the form of statements

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The t test was carried out to determine whether the independent variables partially had a significant effect on the promotion variable (X1) and the interest rate (X2). The degree of confidence used is 0.05. For analysis of SPSS 25 output, you can see the following table:

Tabel 1. Partial Test (t Test)
Uji Parsial (Uji t)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-,293	,048		-6,119	,000
	Promosi	,260	,059	,242	4,431	,000
	Tingkat suku bunga	,772	,057	,745	13,627	,000

Dependent Variable: Keputusan nasabah (Y)

Sumber: Data Primer (Kuesioner), diolah 2023

According to the preceding table, the interest rate variable (X2) has a calculated t value of 13.627 and the promotion variable (X1) has a calculated t value of 4.431 with a significant value of 0.000. The following equation can be used to determine the value of the t table in the partial test (t test):

$$\text{Table } t = t (\alpha / 2; n - k - 1)$$

$$= t (0,05 / 2; 336 - 3 - 1)$$

$$= t (0,025; 332) = 1,967$$

With a confidence level of 0.05, the distribution of t table values yields the t table value of 1.967, which means:

1. A notable impact of the promotional variable (X1) is seen on customers' decisions to buy consumer products at PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch. This can be seen from the significant value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05 and the calculated t value of 4.431 which is greater than the t table of 1.967.
2. The interest rate variable (X2) has a significant effect on customers' decisions to buy consumer products at PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch. This can be seen from the significant value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05 and the calculated t value of 13.627 which is greater than the t table of 1.967.

b. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

The simultaneous test, also known as the F test (F statistical test), is a technique in statistical analysis that is used to assess whether a group of independent variables together have a significant influence on the dependent variable in a statistical model. This test is often used in the context of regression

analysis, both simple linear regression and multiple linear regression. Simultaneous tests are carried out to assess whether the independent variables together have a significant influence on the dependent variable. The confidence level used in this test is 0.05. If given that the significance value is less than 0.05, it can be said that the independent variable and dependent variable are significantly influenced by one another at the same time.

The results of the simultaneous test analysis or F test have been carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software, and the results are presented in the table below:

Tabel 2. Simultaneous Test
Hasil Uji Simultan (Uji F)

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	243,698	2	121,849	5035,590	,000 ^b
	Residual	8,058	333	,024		
	Total	251,756	335			

a. *Dependent Variable: Keputusan nasabah (Y)*

b. *Predictors: (Constant), Tingkat suku bunga, Promosi*

Sumber: Data Primer (Kuesioner), diolah 2023

From the table above, the calculated F value is 5,035.590 with a significant value of 0.000. To determine the calculated F value, it is necessary to have degrees of freedom in the numerator and degrees of freedom in the denominator, with the following formula:

- df (numerator) = $k - 1$
- df (denominator) = $n - k$

Information:

n = number of research samples

k = number of independent and dependent variables

In this study, it is known that the number of samples (n) is 336 and the total number of variables (k) is 3, so we get:

$$F \text{ table} = F (k-1; n - k)$$

$$= F (3-1; 336 - 3)$$

$$= F (2; 333) = 3,023$$

The F table value of 3.023 is derived from the table distribution of F values with a 0.05 confidence level using the equation above. Consequently, the Sig value is $0.000 < 0.05$ and the calculated F value is $5,035,590 > F$ table value 3.023, which means that promotions (X1) and interest rates (X2) simultaneously influence customer decisions on consumer products at PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch (Y).

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination (R²)

This coefficient of determination is used to find out what percentage influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. For analysis of the SPSS 25 output, you can see the following table

Tabel 3. Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Hasil Analisis Koefisien Determinasi (R²)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,984 ^a	,968	,968	,15556

a. Predictors: (Constant), tingkat suku bunga, promosi
 Sumber: Data Primer (Kuesioner), diolah 2023

The aforementioned table's R² value of 0.968 indicates that promotions (X1) and interest rates (X2) on customer decisions (Y) have an influence of 0.968 or (96.8%), while the remainder is 0.032 or (3.2 %) is influenced by other variables that are not the variables studied.

In the context of this research, researchers will discuss issues related to the influence of promotions and interest rates on the decisions of ASN customers who choose consumer products at PT Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch. Based on the results of several tests that have been carried out, the results of the data testing are described as follows:

1. Effect of Promotion on Customer Decisions

According to the results of the partial tests carried out, there is strong evidence that promotions have a significant influence on customer decisions. This is reinforced by the calculated t value of 4.431 > t table 1.967, with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05. The study's findings are predicated on an examination of respondents' comments concerning promotional elements, such as promotional messages, media used, promotional times, and promotional frequency. From this analysis, it can be concluded that the promotion carried out by PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch can be considered effective. One aspect that is very supportive is the long promotional period, which received positive responses from 204 customers, which is equivalent to 61% of the total sample.

Apart from that, frequent advertising of consumer products on social media also has a positive impact on customer decisions. Data shows that 180 customers, or around 54% of all respondents, felt interested in this product because advertisements for this product often appeared on social media. This indicates that the use of social media as a promotional platform has an important role in influencing customer preferences. The use of long-term

promotions and an active presence on social media helps banks build ongoing awareness of the products or services they offer, thereby providing more opportunities for customers to understand and consider the product before making a purchasing decision. consider the product before making a purchasing decision.

The Influence of Interest Rates on Customer Decisions Based on the results of the partial test that has been carried out, it was found that the calculated t value for the interest rate variable is $13.627 > t$ table 1.967 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. These results strongly indicate that interest rates have a significant influence on customer decisions. This study's findings are predicated on an examination of the replies given by respondents replies interest rates. Respondents were asked to provide their views by considering indicators such as interest rates, interest rate determination, interest charges, interest rate comparisons, and interest rate assignments. In general, responses from respondents illustrate that the interest rate applied by PT. Bank Sulsebar Parepare Branch is considered very good

Customers' trust in the bank's compliance with government interest standards is one of the strong reasons why they choose to take consumer products from this bank. In a competitive economic environment, an interest rate that meets standards can be a determining factor in a customer's decision to entrust their money to a financial institution. Thus, the results of this study highlight the importance of PT compliance. Bank Sulsebar Parepare Branch towards government regulations in building strong relationships with customers and increasing their market share in the financial sector.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering the results of investigation and discussions that have been carried out regarding the influence of promotions and interest rates on the decisions of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) customers in taking consumer credit at PT. Bank Sulsebar Parepare Branch, from this study, the following findings can be made:

1. Partial Test

Considering the outcomes of the partial test, the calculated t value for the promotion variable t calculated 4.431 is greater than the t table 1.967 with a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05 , this shows that promotion has a significant effect on the decision of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) customers in taking credit consumer at PT. Bank Sulsebar Parepare Branch. Meanwhile, regarding the interest rate variable, partially the interest rate (X₂) has a positive and significant effect on the decisions of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) customers in taking consumer credit at PT. Bank Sulsebar Parepare Branch. This is indicated by the calculated t value of 13.627 which is greater than the t table of 1.967 with a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05 .

2. Simultaneous Test

Based on the results of the simultaneous test, the calculated F value is 5035.590, which is greater than the F table value of 3.023 having a significance level below 0.05, or a significance value of 0.000. This explains why interest rates and promotions have a big impact on things at the same time. the decisions of Civil Service customers. State (ASN) in taking consumer credit at PT. Bank Sulselbar Parepare Branch. The value of R² is 0.968 which indicates that promotion (X1) and interest rates (X2) on performance (Y) have an influence of 0.968 or (96.8%), while the remaining 0.032 or (3.2%) is influenced by factors others not examined by researchers.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "The Influence of Promotions and Interest Rates on ASN Customer Decisions in Taking Consumer Credit PT Bank Sulselbar Cabang Parepare."

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